

Digital Economy

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***Annotation.** In a world moving toward the era of the digital economy, the global economy has been transformed, shaking the traditional relationships between individuals, enterprises, and society, and digitalizing the mode of social production.*

***Keywords:** digital economy; industrial restructuring; human capital; technological innovation; financial development*

INTRODUCTION

Digital technology is the representation of information in bits. This reduces the cost of storage, computation, and transmission of data. Research on digital economics examines whether and how digital technology changes economic activity. Understanding the effects of digital technology does not require fundamentally new economic theory. However, it requires a different emphasis. Studying digital economics starts with the question of “what is different?” What is easier to do when information is represented by bits rather than atoms? Digital technology often means that costs that may constrain economic actions. Therefore, digital economics explores how standard economic models change as certain costs fall substantially and perhaps approach zero. We emphasize how this shift in costs can be divided into five types:

1. Lower search costs
2. Lower replication costs
3. Lower transportation costs
4. Lower tracking costs
5. Lower verification costs

Search costs are lower in digital environments, enlarging the potential scope and quality of search. Digital goods can be replicated at zero cost, meaning they are often non-rival. The role of geographic distance changes as the cost of transportation for digital goods and information is approximately zero. Digital technologies make it easy to track any one individual's behavior. Last, digital verification can make it easier to verify the reputation and trustworthiness of any one individual, firm, or organization in the digital economy. Each of these cost changes draws on a different set of well-established economic models: Primarily search models, non-rival goods models, transportation cost models, price discrimination models, and reputation models.

Early research tested straightforward models of lower costs. For example, the search literature of the late 1990s and early 2000s built directly on earlier models by Diamond (1971) and Varian (1980). As we detail below, empirical work emerged that found some inconsistencies with the simple models, and so richer models and empirical analysis of the cost reductions developed to take account of the subtleties of the digital context. Other authors have also emphasized the role of lower costs for digital economics (e.g. Shapiro and Varian (1998), Borenstein and Saloner (2001), Smith et al. (2001), etc.) Ellison 2 and Ellison (2005) the implications of these lower search and transportation costs for industrial organization with respect to increasing returns, distance and two-sided markets. Since their article, the digital economics literature has grown to contribute to the economics of crime, the economics of public goods, organizational economics, finance, urban economics, labor economics, development economics, health economics, political economy, media economics, public finance, and international economics. In this sense, we view digital economics as a way of thinking that touches many fields of economics.

This review starts with a brief history of digital technology and the internet. It will then discuss each of the cost changes associated with digitization. In each section, we emphasize the key research questions that have driven the area and how they have evolved, and relate them to policy where applicable. After discussing each cost change, we finish by discussing the consequences of digitization for countries, regions, firms, and individuals.

One of the most significant changes that we experience today is the move to an Internet-based society. Some of the changes are already here, and they are spreading around the globe, others are just beginning. One of the most significant changes is in the manner we conduct business, especially in how we manage the marketplaces and commerce. Electronic commerce (e-commerce) refers to the way in which transactions take place over networks, mostly the Internet. E-commerce facilitates the growth and dynamic development of the digital economy, taking place in the digital ecosystem.

The digital economy, also known as the Internet economy, new economy, or the Web economy, refers to the economy that is based in a large part on digital technologies, including digital communications networks (Internet, intranets, etc.), computers, software, and other related information technologies (Turban et al. 2002, p.45). In other words, the term digital economy refers to the convergence of computing and communication technologies through the Internet and the resulting flow of information and technology that is stimulating e-commerce and spurring vast organizational changes.

Digital networking and communication infrastructures provide a global platform to interact, communicate, collaborate and search for information. This unique platform includes the following components:

- A wide area of products made of digital bits - databases, news and information, books, magazines, TV and radio programming, movies, electronic games, musical CDs, and software - that are delivered over the digital infrastructure anytime, anywhere in the world in the 24/7 mode.
- Consumers and firms conduct financial transactions digitally through digital currencies or financial tokens downloaded and carried on smart cards via networked computers and mobile devices.
- Physical goods such as home appliances and automobiles are embedded with microprocessors and networking capabilities (Choi and Whinston 2000).

The digital economy is characterized by the digitization of many products and services and by the use of the Internet and other networks to support economic activities. Such computerization changes the manner in which business is done and considerably improves economic activities and competition. The main issues that are germane to management include the introduction of new business models, different rules in the area of competition, the issue of organizational transformation to the digital economy, the changing role of intermediation (disintermediation and reintermediation), the process of globalization of each aspect of business activity, organizational changes and new business alliances. Practically all functional areas are impacted by the digital economy. Direct marketing and one-to-one marketing are becoming a norm.

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